

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES ON INVESTMENT ATTRACTION MECHANISMS

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Step-by-step implementation of economic reforms in our country and the fact that the state is the main reformer in this process is one of the characteristics of our country's transition to a market economy. This process requires making many decisions regarding the regulation of investment activities. Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "It is necessary to establish strong relations with foreign investors who have expressed a desire to work with Uzbekistan, to help them from the beginning to the end of the project, to put it simply, to lead them by the hand and ensure the result". Sustainable growth of the economy, renewal of the fixed capital and structural changes in the entire investment and financial sphere without proper implementation of investment activities in economic sectors, attraction of domestic and foreign investments and implementation of effective development works cannot be achieved, therefore, these reforms are regulated by the state. The role of foreign investments in the development and improvement of the economic situation of the country is considered important.

The foreign experience of investment attraction and management and a number of researches within the scope of its application in our country are of particular importance in the scientific researches of foreign economists C.Liyebeth, M.Miyet, S.Jo. According to researchers, the process of economic liberalization in transition countries is an important factor in improving the system of attracting foreign direct investment. Attracting technologies and knowledge to national enterprises through direct capital accumulation and technological know-how ensures sustainable rates of economic growth [2].

In the above studies aimed at substantiating the foreign experience of attracting and managing investments and the possibilities of its implementation in our country, the possibilities of ensuring the active pace of investment processes and economic growth by creating macroeconomic conditions were studied. Among the factors that have a positive effect on the growth of investments, the processes related to the high position of private property, the existence of a competitive environment, and the role of the solvent consumer market have not been studied.

After gaining independence, our country has accumulated experience in investment activity for many years. He led an active policy of attracting investments to our economy. That is, according to him, we will dwell on the investment policy of the USA, which is one of the leading countries in the world, the ways of attracting investments and establishing their management, regulation and control.

The USA is a country with a very developed economy and a strong legal system. The US investment climate is bright and attractive enough. Currently, this country occupies one of the leading places in the world in terms of attracting foreign investments. That is, it is about 20% worldwide. In order to achieve such excellent results, the US government allocated the necessary powers to the individual states of the country for foreign investment as an important factor in the development of the economy. That is, according to it, the regional management bodies in the country are given powers no less than the management body of the country in order to encourage the increase of the flow of investments.

The American government is well aware that the introduction of foreign capital into the US economy has a significant impact not only on industry, trade and inflation, but also on the national security of the entire country. As a result:

- states and local government bodies are given independence for the economic development of their territory, private business and export of services and goods should be supported;
- attract foreign business capital and control the foreign investor accordingly;
- stimulating the growth of the private economy;
- must carry out motivational actions in fiscal policy.

The last result shows that these factors have given rise to mutual competition between the states of the country and acted as a special impetus for the development of the law on investments in the country. In this regard, we can distinguish the following important features of attracting and managing investments in the US economy:

- a high flow of investments into the economy is ensured as a result of the regional and national policies;
- the equal level of stimulation of capital export and import, as a result of which the country has the status of a net importer;
- non-allowance of abuse of high level control of foreign investments (corruption, violations of legal norms and financial-credit agreements);

- market openness for other participants;
- development of investment legislation and tax system;
- the existence of a two-level system of investment activity regulation.

It should be noted that the management of investments in the US is based on the principles of economic freedom and does not seriously interfere with the economic process, as this creates an unacceptable limit. Such a goal is the main work of foreign economic activity institutes in the USA, and the government is working to expand the maximum export potential of the country and its regions, to attract as many participants as possible in international economic activity .

The US economy will remain the largest in 2030, but its share of global GDP will fall from 23% in 2021 to 20%. These macroeconomic data were compiled by the US Department of Agriculture by calculating the 20 largest economies in the world by 2030 in terms of gross domestic product.

Figure 1. Countries that will have the world's largest economy in 2030. (trln.doll.) [3]

According to the forecasts, the USA will retain the leadership, and the country's gross domestic product will reach 24.8 trillion by 2030. is a dollar. The second place is occupied by China, whose gross domestic product is 22.2 trillion. consists of dollars. India is the top three with 6.6 trillion. dollar enters with the gross domestic product. The International Monetary Fund notes that in the last 10 years, India will become the strongest country in the world in terms of production power.

One of the leading countries in the world in attracting and

managing investments is China. Their investment management policy is commendable. Because China has risen to the first place in the world in terms of attracting investments, and has pushed the United States, which has not given its place to anyone for several centuries, to the next place. One of its main directions is the policy of promoting investments in the national economy, and is still doing so. China is considered the leader in the world according to its capabilities, and we can point to the internationalization of the research conducted in them and the adoption of transnational corporations as the main factor. Currently, more than 1,000 scientific and research organizations created at the expense of foreign funds are operating in the country. Practice shows that the scientific approach and capital-intensive sectors are quickly becoming an important direction for the introduction of foreign capital.

Also, by the end of 2021, an index of trust of foreign direct investors of the last three years was developed in the Internet networks of the countries. You can see the full form of this table below.

Table 1. Confidence index of foreign direct investors as of the end of 2021.[4]

Countries	2020 year	2021 year
USA	1	1
China	2	2
Great Britain	4	8
Canada	3	4
Germany	6	7

According to Table 1, the first place was taken by the USA, followed by China and Great Britain. You can see this chart below. Based on foreign experience, it is possible to say that the energy sector of our country can increase efficiency by applying these account books and putting them into practice. Account books are listed below and are being implemented.

In addition, detailed theoretical information was given about forfeiting and selening methods, which are just entering practice. The legal basis of attracting investments and their management is presented. In this plan, a description of various regulatory legal documents valid in the territory of our country, regulating and helping to manage investment activities is shown. In

addition, the main persons making investments in our country, that is, the opportunities created for investors and the obligations imposed on the participants of the investment activities, are also explained in detail. In the coverage of this plan, a wide range of information was provided through the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Investment Activities. However, it should be noted that in the period of economic development and modernization of our country, it is necessary to further improve the existing laws in our republic and partially liberalize the functioning of the existing legal mechanisms. Through this, it opens the possibility of attracting new investment funds by introducing simple mechanisms to investors and investors, leading to simplification and easy understanding of the regulatory framework.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the content of the economic reforms carried out in our country is the successful introduction of a socially oriented market economy. Laws adopted in our country create clear socio-legal foundations for the formation of a multi-level economy, which allows for the widespread use of socially oriented market relations. The influence and position of Uzbekistan in the international economic arena is growing significantly and regularly. In this case, the head of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, carefully developed the strategy of socio- economic development, the goals and tasks of economic reforms, and the clear and correct indication of the ways of implementation, made it possible to achieve significant achievements and milestones on the way to the main goal. created

To study the experience of developed countries, the way they have traveled, the laws they have adopted to improve the investment climate of the country, the decisions they have made in order to ensure economic development, the methods they have developed for attracting investments, and Applying the necessary aspects of the methods to the conditions of Uzbekistan is considered one of the most important issues. After all, the application of the accumulated experiences, taking into account the specific characteristics of the country, leads to the reduction of risks, the prevention of abstraction, and the provision of high efficiency.

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